

Trash2Danger - A two-stage deep learning based pipeline for marine debris ecological danger level evaluations

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Abstract

Marine debris, defined as man-made litter found on beaches and in oceans, represents a significant ecological threat. In general, beach cleanup efforts aim to intercept marine debris before it reaches the ocean, where it can cause extensive environmental harm. These efforts are more efficient when debris with higher ecological risk is prioritized; however, targeted cleanup based on danger levels is rarely implemented. Currently, assessing the ecological threat posed by specific types and locations of marine debris typically requires a human expert evaluation, which can be costly and difficult to obtain. In recent years, machine learning-based object detection has been applied to environmental cleanup efforts for marine debris detection, with drones equipped with cameras that are used for identification and classification. However, automating the danger evaluation component of this process remains unexplored. In this paper, we propose a novel method that combines computer vision and marine debris cleanup, with the goal of designing a model that not only classifies types of marine debris, but also predicts a relative ecological danger rating for each item. A key consideration in the model design was to ensure that it was lightweight enough for deployment in UAVs (unmanned aerial vehicles). The model was trained to assign danger ratings to marine debris, reflecting their relative ecological risks, thus allowing volunteers to concentrate cleanup efforts on high-risk areas. Our two-stage model integrates traditional object detection and classification with a separate neural network that assigns danger ratings. To evaluate the effectiveness of the model, we developed a benchmark that compares the model's danger predictions to expert assessments from marine biology. We tested the model on the beaches of Dapeng Bay, Shenzhen, China, and observed promising results in its relative danger evaluations compared to expert evaluations. Future testing in diverse marine environments is needed and will allow for a more comprehensive analysis of the model's capabilities.

The code for our model is available at: [Github](#).

Keywords: Marine Debris, Object Detection, Danger Evaluation, Deep Learning

1. Introduction

Marine debris poses a serious threat to marine environments [1]. The spread of marine debris has been linked to the reduction of biodiversity [2], as well as having significant effects on marine food chains [3]. Ingestion of marine debris has been documented in 1,400 species of marine fauna [4], and the ingestion of only a single piece of marine debris can cause the death of marine animals [5]. Furthermore, marine debris in the ocean can take years to decompose, often leaving toxic chemicals that affect the environment [6, 7]. The vast majority of marine debris comes from land and beaches [8].

Around the globe, marine debris cleanup has become more and more prominent, with many volunteer efforts attempting to remove marine debris from beaches before they reach the ocean and cause ecological damage. To allow marine debris cleanup efforts to be efficient and effective, volunteers need to know which specific pieces of marine debris pose the greatest threats to the environment, so those pieces can be the focus of removal. Currently, human experts must be on site to perform this kind of evaluation. These experts need to evaluate areas of marine debris to decide which areas have marine debris that pose the greatest threat and on which cleanup efforts should be focused.

However, this type of expert evaluation is not always available or used, due to the cost of hiring experts and the inherent complexity of this solution. Often, cleanup efforts simply try to clean up every single piece of marine debris possible, regardless of environmental threat, leading to

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cleanup efforts that are less effective and inefficient. Many attempts have been made to automate parts of the marine debris cleanup process, such as detecting pieces of marine debris using computer vision techniques [9, 10, 11]. However, currently there is no way to automate the risk assessment part of the marine debris cleanup process, which is key to effective cleanups.

Recent attempts to automate the marine debris cleanup process have been focused on utilizing computer vision and machine learning to detect and classify pieces of marine debris. Object detection models, such as the YOLO [12], Faster RCNN [13], and DETR [14] series, have been trained on images of marine debris to aid in the detection and classification of marine debris [9, 10, 11]. When paired with camera-equipped drones, these models have the potential to massively improve waste cleanup efforts.

However, what these drone-based marine debris detection systems lack is a way to classify the danger levels of individual pieces of debris. Individual pieces of marine debris vary in material, size, chemical composition, toxicity, and decomposition time; therefore, individual pieces of debris will pose vastly different ecological threats and dangers. The ability to assign danger levels to individual pieces of marine debris would allow for more focused cleanup efforts, since higher-risk pieces of debris could be targeted more intensively.

In this paper, we propose a two-stage AI model that first detects and classifies pieces of marine debris and then predicts a danger/risk score for each instance of marine debris in the image, allowing for more efficient prioritization in cleanup efforts. This model combines a standard object detection model, trained to detect and classify marine debris, with a ResNet model [15], trained to predict a danger score from 1-3 for each instance of debris detected in an image. The first stage, the detector, feeds all detected pieces of marine debris into the danger level prediction stage, which outputs a danger level evaluation for each piece of debris. At the same time, this model was intended to be used in drone-based applications; thus, low latency and a small model size were also a priority.

The two-stage architecture was adopted for greater modularity and adaptability for the danger ranking predictions, as well as lowering training computation costs. Ideally, the computed heavy object detection model would only need to be trained once on the classes of marine debris for universal usage, while the smaller, danger-level prediction head could be calibrated for different applications. For example, when the model is applied to an area with greater UV exposure, the danger levels of UV sensitive plastic types could be adjusted accordingly [16]. Rather than training a large object detection model multiple different times to output danger levels in different scenarios, only the small danger level predictor would need to be trained to be used in different environments. This allows the model to be applied

in a variety of environments without the significant training computational cost of retraining a single larger, all-in-one model.

There were no preexisting data or "ground truth" values that provided the actual danger values for each piece of debris, since there exists no quantitative way to measure the danger of a piece of marine debris. Therefore, to evaluate the effectiveness of the model, its outputs were compared with the assessments on the danger of marine debris made by a group of experts. The experts manually assigned danger scores to each piece of debris. This comparison served as a benchmark to gauge the model's accuracy and reliability. In doing so, the ultimate goal was for the model to perform at a level comparable to or better than these experts. This would indicate that the model was successful in learning to predict the danger posed by the marine debris.

We applied the marine debris detection and danger level prediction model to beaches with marine debris in Dapeng, Shenzhen, China, using videos and images from drones. Our model achieved promising results when compared to the experts' evaluations on these images.

With this work, we hope to achieve a light-weight model that can competently output detections, classifications, and danger predictions for marine debris, ultimately improving the viability of drone-based cleanup efforts.

Our contributions are as follows.

1. Propose a two-stage modular network for marine debris detection and danger level prediction.
2. Propose a method to benchmark the danger level predictions of the model against expert predictions on the same instances of marine debris.

2. Model Architecture

The model is made up of two stages. A detection and classification stage that outputs bounding box and classification predictions for marine debris and a second stage that outputs a danger/risk level prediction for each piece of marine debris. For each instance of marine debris detected by the Stage 1 model, the bounding box for that piece of marine debris is cropped out, resized, and fed to the danger prediction model for evaluation. Figure 1 illustrates this overall model architecture.

2.1. Stage 1: Detection and Classification

The first stage, which takes an input image and outputs bounding box and class predictions, can be any object detection and classification model that outputs bounding box information. The Yolo series [12], Faster RCNN series [13], and the transformer DETR series [14], among others, would all be suitable for stage 1 application. In our implementation, we chose the Yolov8 [17] model, specifically, the 3.2 million parameter Yolov8-nano model, due to its small size, low inference time, and due to its state-of-the-art level per-

Figure 1. Overall pipeline of our model and system

Table 1. A comparison of smaller size detection models trained on our dataset, all inferences run on an Nvidia RTX A6000

Model	#Params(M)	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95	Total Inference Time(ms)
Yolov8n	3.2	0.761	0.642	0.692	0.356	27.8
Yolov10n	2.3	0.777	0.595	0.669	0.339	30.8

formance amongst models of the same size. Table 1 is a comparison of various object detection models of similar size on our dataset:

As can be seen from Table 1, Yolov8-n performs the best after being trained on our dataset, while simultaneously having the least latency.

We also trained and tested various larger models on our dataset. These have a larger latency in predictions, and would most likely not be able to be used in lightweight, drone-based applications, but could be used to process other videos. Table 2 shows the results from these larger models.

2.2. Stage 2: Danger Level Prediction

After the 1st stage predicts bounding box and class information, those bounding boxes are cropped out of the image, and fed to a ResNet [15] model which is in charge of predicting a danger/risk level for each predicted piece of marine debris outputted by stage 1. Each cropped bounding box is put in the center of a 400×400 pixel image, and any bounding box with dimensions greater than 400×400 pixels was sized down to fit while maintaining aspect ratio.

This is the same as what was done in creating the training dataset. This was done to maintain relative size between pieces of marine debris. These cropped images are then scaled down to 224×224 pixels and fed into the ResNet model. The input size of 224×224 for our ResNet model was chosen to align with standard input requirements for pre-trained ResNet architectures, enabling us to leverage the model’s full potential. While resizing all bounding boxes to this dimension required some padding, this approach allowed us to preserve relative size information, which was important for the prediction of relative danger level prediction. A smaller input size would have reduced the padding required to get the smaller bounding boxes to the correct input size, but would have increased the down scaling needed for the larger bounding boxes that exceeded the input size dimensions, which would have led to less preservation of relative size information. Additionally, reducing the input size may have affected the model’s ability to detect fine-grained features of the debris items, which could impact the accuracy of the danger level classification. Our approach seeks to balance the need for computational efficiency with

Table 2. A comparison of larger size detection models trained on our dataset, all inferences run on an Nvidia RTX A6000

Model	#Params(M)	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95	Total Inference Time(ms)
Yolov8-l	43.7	0.840	0.708	0.727	0.389	30.9
Yolov10-l	24.4	0.837	0.688	0.717	0.387	36.8
RT-DETR-l	42.0	0.857	0.714	0.710	0.363	108.5

the preservation of essential visual information.

During training the stage 2 model, the labels on the cropped images are discrete integer values between 1 and 3, and the model is trained to optimally assign danger values of 1, 2, or 3. However, during inference, the model can output either this discrete danger-level prediction or a continuous danger-level value: the weighted average of the Softmax of the class predictions it used as the final danger level prediction. That way, the model can also represent danger levels continuously, rather than three discrete values. The model outputs discrete predictions, y_{discrete} as follows:

$$y_{\text{discrete}} = \text{argmax}(\text{Softmax}(z))$$

Where z represents the output values from the final fully connected layers of the ResNet model [15].

The continuous prediction, $y_{\text{continuous}}$ is calculated as the weighted average of the Softmax outputs:

$$y_{\text{continuous}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 i \cdot \text{Softmax}(z_i)$$

Where z_i are the individual fully connected layer outputs for each class $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. This formulation allows the model to represent danger levels continuously, rather than limiting predictions to just three discrete values.

Throughout our testing, we used two different models for the danger level predictions: The Resnet 50 model and the Resnet 18 model. Through our testing (See Benchmark), the Resnet 50 model performed better at assigning these danger levels (See Results and Discussion) and so the Resnet 50 model was chosen for our final stage 2 application.

The two-stage architecture was adopted for greater modularity and adaptability for the danger ranking predictions without significantly increasing training computation costs. With a single stage model that outputs both detections and the danger level predictions, the entire model would need to be retrained for different applications. With a two stage model, ideally, the larger, compute heavy object detection model would only need to be trained once on the classes of marine debris so it can be used universally, while the smaller, danger level prediction head could be calibrated for different applications. This allows the model to be applied in a variety of environments without significantly increasing training costs. The computation cost of training an object detection model is much greater than the cost for train-

ing the danger level prediction model (See Model Training). An example of a use case for this 2 stage modularity is as follows: research shows that polyethylene plastics pose a significant threat to seabirds [18]. In an area with a large seabird population, the danger levels of specifically polyethylene marine debris could be adjusted and trained into the stage 2 danger level predictor, without needing to retrain the stage 1 debris detector. Another example would be for an area with higher UV exposure; the danger levels of UV sensitive types of plastics could be adjusted accordingly [16].

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Data Collection

In order to train a model on marine debris detection, classification, and then danger level prediction, a sufficiently large, diverse, well-labelled dataset on images of marine debris was needed. Data was collected from two sources:

1. UAV images taken manually by our team
2. Images taken from two online datasets of marine debris at various angles and lighting (Open source datasets used: [19, 20]).

All images were restricted to only containing marine debris on the beach; any images containing debris in water were omitted.

The UAV images were taken in Dapeng Bay, Shenzhen, China, chosen due to its close geographical proximity to Shenzhen, and its large tourism industry, meaning that a large quantity of marine debris and litter would be available on its beaches. A Dji Mini 2 and a Dji Mavic were utilized for aerial image capture. The Dji Mini utilized a 12MP sensor shooting 4K video at 30fps; the Dji Mavic also utilized a 12MP sensor shooting 4K video at 30fps. These drones were chosen as they are both standard, "consumer-grade" drones capable of shooting at high resolutions (>4k). The drones were flown manually, maintaining an altitude of no greater than 10m above the beach floor, while making sure the ocean was within 50m of the drone's flight path. The drones were manually flown over areas with a high density of marine litter. Both drones were capturing video at 4k constantly as they were flown. Videos were captured under varying weather conditions, on two different days. Afterwards, frames from the videos with marine debris were selected as training images, with each image covering an area of approximately 10 square meters. Images were taken at a

range of heights from 1-10m and from a variety of camera angles (0 - 90°).

Select images were taken from online open source marine debris datasets. Certain classes of marine debris were underrepresented in the UAV images, and so images selected from the open source datasets were meant to balance out this under-representation; thus, images containing instances of the marine debris classes that were underrepresented were selected from the online datasets. These images provided greater balance in class distribution while simultaneously offering a greater diversity in camera angles and lighting, adding robustness to the dataset.

3.2. Dataset Generation & Danger Level Labeling

After collecting data from the above 2 methods, the dataset was annotated on class, bounding box information, and then danger level. It was decided to sort the marine debris present in the dataset into 7 classes of common marine debris types. These 7 classes were all commonly occurring were all present in a substantive number of instances within our dataset, and represented almost all the marine debris that was encountered. The 7 classifications were as follows:

1. Can
2. Carton
3. Plastic bag
4. Plastic bottle
5. Plastic container
6. Styrofoam
7. Tire

Any marine debris that didn't fit any of these classifications were simply ignored and therefore not labelled, however there were very few instances of this. For each image, each instance of one of these classes of marine debris was given a rectangular bounding box and a classification. This labeling of the larger full images was for training the Detection and Classification stage of the model. The second stage that predicted the danger level would only be fed the cropped bounding box predictions from the detection stage, and it would predict based on that smaller, cropped image.

To generate the dataset for the danger level prediction stage of the model, the individual annotated bounding boxes were cropped out of the original, larger images, resulting in multiple smaller, cropped images per original image, each containing an instance of marine debris. These cropped bounding box images were then placed in the center of a 400 pixel by 400 pixel black image. Any bounding boxes larger than 400 × 400 pixels were scaled down to fit while maintaining aspect ratio. Bounding boxes that fit these dimensions, however, were not rescaled. The goal of this was to maximally maintain the relative sizes of each instance of marine debris, as that would be important to the danger level for each piece of debris.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of marine debris ingestion and its impacts on different animal groups based on a survey. (a) Total deaths attributed to different types of marine debris by animal group. (b) Proportion of deaths within each group caused by specific debris items. (c) Commonness of debris ingestion, measured by the frequency of ingested items that resulted in death. (d) Lethality of ingested items, showing the proportion of ingested debris that led to death across different animal groups. Groups include cetaceans, pinnipeds, sea turtles, and seabirds (adapted from [5]).

The individual, cropped images of each piece of debris were labeled on a discrete value between 1-3, corresponding to the below risk/danger levels:

- 1- Low Danger
- 2- Moderate Danger
- 3- High Danger

A 3 level approach was used as it was relatively straightforward for labeling, however, an approach with greater differentiation in levels (See Discussion) would also work. Since our danger prediction model was capable of outputting a continuous prediction, the weighted average of the Softmax predicted values for each class, the model theoretically still had flexibility in its predictions, not just limited to these 3 discrete levels. To split each instance of marine debris into one of these 3 danger/risk levels, both biological and environmental research was considered. Since well defined, quantitative metrics that evaluate the danger level of marine debris do not exist, we devised a simple ranking system of 3 levels of danger based on our research. The effects of various types of marine debris, including the animal deaths they caused, their toxicity, and their degradation time, were all considered when determining the danger level. Based on the research, it was decided to put the marine debris into the 3 danger levels as shown in Table 3.

Cartons, being made of paper and cardboard, were put in the low danger classification due to the relative ease of decomposition of paper and cardboard and low ingestion risk [5]. Although metal is moderately lethal when ingested [5], cans were also placed in the low danger category due to a low ingestion rate by marine megafauna [21]. Altogether, paper, glass and metal account for less than 2% of

Table 3. How the Danger levels (1-3) were assigned to each class of marine debris

1(Low)	2(Medium)	3(High)
Small Styrofoam	Medium Styrofoam	Large Styrofoam
Cartons	Tires	Plastic Bags
Cans	Small Plastic Containers	Large Plastic Containers
		Plastic Bottles

marine debris ingestion encounters [22]. Both cans and cartons don't decompose into toxic chemicals. Cans, being made of tin, don't pose any significant toxic threat to marine environments, as they mostly don't contain any heavy metals [23].

Tires, being composed of rubber, pose a relatively moderate threat to marine fauna. This is due to their relatively low ingestion rate, but high lethality when ingested [5]. Rubber tires, when intact, have been shown to not have any significant negative ecological impact, even being viable as artificial reefs on which benthic communities can flourish [24]. However, smaller pieces of rubber that can come off of the larger tires can pose an ingestion threat, so overall, tires are assigned a moderate danger level.

Plastics are by far the most prominent, most frequently encountered type of marine debris in oceans and on beaches [25], with plastic ingestion causing the majority of documented marine animal deaths from marine debris [5]. Microplastics (<5 mm) have been shown to be the most detrimental to marine environments and animals, causing the most animal deaths and leading to the largest increases in water toxicity [26, 25]. Therefore, the danger of the plastic marine debris classes was assigned based on how easily they degraded into microplastics and the type of microplastics they formed. Plastic bottles, being primarily made of Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), degrade into microplastics relatively easily, especially when exposed to water and sunlight [27], and were therefore given a high danger rating.

Styrofoam (foamed polystyrene) and plastic containers had rather large size distributions, with many different observed sizes. The danger level of particular pieces of plastic or polystyrene would be dependent on their size, since larger pieces would fragment into more microplastics [28]. As such, these two classes were split into risk levels based on the sizes of individual instances of these classes. For Styrofoam, the areas of each bounding box instance were calculated. Then, based on this calculated area, each instance was assigned a danger level. Areas in the largest, middle, and lowest third of the distribution were sorted into the high, moderate, and low danger levels respectively. A similar methodology was used to label danger levels for the plastic containers. However, we only assigned danger levels of high risk and moderate risk to the plastic containers, since even the relatively smaller sized plastic contain-

ers would pose a threat [5, 25]. For the plastic containers, instances that had areas in the larger half of the distribution were assigned high danger and the smaller half were assigned moderate danger. The rest of the classes had relatively even size distributions, and as such weren't sorted depending on size.

Standard data augmentation techniques, like flipping, rotation, increased noise, and shear were applied to both the dataset of original images, as well as the cropped images, to add robustness. The datasets were split into training, validation, and testing sets in the ratio of 85% : 10% : 5% respectively.

3.3. Model Training

All the models were trained on a PC with an Nvidia RTX A6000 GPU. Table 4 and Table 5 contain information on the training parameters.

The Resnet 50 and 18 models achieved R^2 values for their continuous predictions of 0.6297 and 0.5329 respectively. These R^2 values between our model's continuous risk predictions and expert assessments reflect the degree of alignment between the model and expert judgments in evaluating ecological danger levels of marine debris. The moderately high R^2 value of 0.6297 for the Resnet 50 model suggests that the model is reasonably effective in replicating expert evaluation patterns, while the Resnet 18's moderate R^2 value of 0.5329 indicates that it's only moderately effective at replicating the expert's evaluations.

The continuous prediction values only varied greatly from the discrete value intervals when an instance of marine debris wasn't clearly distinguishable to the model. As an example, for an instance of marine debris that looked like both a plastic bottle and a medium sized piece of styrofoam, the model outputted a continuous prediction of 2.49. In similar cases, where the type of marine debris wasn't clear, these continuous predictions were useful, as they indicated which danger levels the piece of debris was between based on its appearance. However, for the instances of debris that were clear, the weighted average was often very close to a whole number, since the model's confidence was high and was trained to minimize the outputs that are wrong. This is evident from Figure 4a and 4b, as there are 3 clusters of closely packed points where the model predicted 1, 2, and 3, and the rest of the points in between are more scattered.

Report on Marine Debris

Marine Debris Classes

Numbers for each class

can: 1
 carton: 3
 plastic bag: 5
 plastic bottle: 4
 plastic con: 6
 styrofoam: 1
 tire: 0

Total: 20

(a) Class Distribution Information

Marine Debris Danger Levels

Numbers for each danger level

Danger Level Low(1): 3
 Danger Level Medium(2): 8
 Danger Level High(3): 9

Average danger level: 2.30
 Median Danger Level: 2.08

(b) Danger Level Distribution Information

Figure 3. Example of two pages from the report detailing class and danger distribution after the model was run on a video of marine debris collected from Dapeng Bay.

Table 4. The training parameters that were used to train the stage 1, marine debris detection and classification models. All were trained on an Nvidia RTX A6000

Model	Epochs	Batch	Image Size	Learning Rate	Momentum	Flops (B)	#Training Images
Yolov8n	200	16	608 × 1024	0.01	0.937	8.7	480
Yolov10n	200	16	608 × 1024	0.01	0.937	6.7	480
Yolov8-l	200	16	608 × 1024	0.01	0.937	165.2	480
Yolov10-l	200	16	608 × 1024	0.01	0.937	120.3	480
RT-DETR-l	200	16	608 × 1024	0.01	0.937	136	480

These points that are in between the whole number values are generally farther from being aligned with the experts' scores, since they indicate that the model is unsure on these more ambiguous pieces of marine debris. When predicting with continuous values, the models' predictions that don't match the experts' consistently seem to be higher than the expert evaluations, indicating that the model overestimates the danger level of pieces of marine debris more often than it underestimates the danger level. This is possibly due to certain pieces of marine debris appearing larger in images due to perspective, leading to higher danger predictions from the model, whereas the human experts were able to intuitively

gauge the actual size of those pieces of marine debris.

The stage 2 danger level predictor, designed to be modular, might benefit from being trained on a greater number of danger levels. Having experts rank pieces of marine debris in terms of danger, not only from 1-3, but on a larger scale, like from 1-10, and then training the model to output danger levels from 1-10, might provide the model with a greater degree of expression and an ability to more accurately reflect the danger levels of marine debris. Furthermore, a greater number of danger levels may allow the model's continuous outputs to be more variable. The benefit of a two-stage model means that the second stage can

Table 5. The training parameters that were used to train the danger prediction, stage 2, Resnet models. All were trained on an Nvidia RTX A6000

Model	Epochs	Batch	Image Size	Learning Rate	Momentum	Flops (B)	#Training Images
Resnet18	300	32	224 × 224	0.001	0.9	1.82	3169
Resnet50	300	32	224 × 224	0.001	0.9	4.12	3169

(a) Resnet 50 hexbin plot

(b) Resnet 18 hexbin plot

Figure 4. Hexbin plots comparing the continuous mean expert danger level predictions with the continuous weighted average danger outputs of the two Resnet models, where the red line represents perfect alignment between the experts’ and model’s predictions. Each Hexbin represents the number of values within a particular range of values, with more yellow hexbins indicating a greater number of values within that range.

Table 6. Accuracy, and R^2 for the Resnet 50 and Resnet 18 stage 2 models. Accuracy was calculated from comparing the model’s discrete predictions with the expert’s discrete predictions. Where R^2 was calculated with the continuous predictions and evaluations

Model	Accuracy	R^2
Resnet 50	0.8125	0.6297
Resnet 18	0.7656	0.5329

be retrained and tested without needing to retrain the stage 1 model, meaning that all of these different methods can be tested and implemented with relative ease.

Furthermore, the assigning of the 3 danger levels to each instance of marine debris in the stage 2 training set was done rather arbitrarily based on scientific research, intuition, and some opinions provided by experts. An alternative approach to assigning the danger levels in the training set would be to have the experts assign danger level predic-

tions to each image in the training set first, and then have the model train directly on these images and values that have already been evaluated by experts. However, with the large number of images in our stage 2 training dataset, it wouldn’t have been feasible for the experts to manually evaluate each piece of debris individually in the training set.

The stage 1 object detection model, for which the Yolov8n model was used, achieved a precision and recall of 0.761 and 0.642 on our validation images. Better results on the validation images for the stage 1 object detector were achieved with the larger model sizes; however, they were too large to be effective in lightweight drone applications. Better training results possibly could have been achieved with a greater number of training images from drones. In many of the photos of the beach floor from the aerial drone view, the pieces of marine debris were very small, and so further drone images from a variety of heights and angles could have added to the robustness of the stage 1 model. The stage 1 model is limited in the number of marine debris

est ecological risks, emulating the effect of having human experts in the field evaluating the danger levels of marine debris. Further research needs to be done on the danger level predictions in varying environments, as well as other ways to rank the danger levels of pieces of marine debris.

Future work includes further testing of the model in varying conditions and geographic regions, which would be needed to verify the robustness of the danger level prediction capabilities under different circumstances. Application to different types of beaches in varying climates and with varying ecosystems would require training the model to evaluate danger levels for those particular environments, since the threat of marine debris is different in every environment. Furthermore, conducting a long-term study to evaluate the impact of targeted cleanups driven by Trash2Danger risk assessments would provide valuable data on the effectiveness of our model. Tracking changes in local ecosystems and debris accumulation rates over time could offer evidence of how targeted, risk-based cleanups contribute to ecosystem health and biodiversity conservation.

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